

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Online service for use of citizen information from smartphone apps for rapid earthquake detection and location estimation (EEW) – (Joint Deliverable with RISE project)

TURNkey

Deliverable D3.7

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12/10/2022	2.0	Final Draft	Final

LIST OF PARTNERS

Participant	Name	Country
NOR	Stiftelsen NORSAR	Norway
DEL	Stichting Deltares	Netherlands
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut	Netherlands
BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	France
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
UIce	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
UStr	University of Strathclyde	UK
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

INDEX OF CONTENTS

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY	i
LIST OF PARTNERS	i
Index of contents	ii
Links	1

PRELIMINARY REMARK

The present Deliverable D3.7 is associated with Deliverable D3.6, with which it shares the same title. D3.6 is a report presenting in detail the method and its performance. D3.7 is not a report, and falls under the category “OTHER”. Its objective is to show where the service is available. This explains the brevity of the D3.7 but all the details are available in D3.6 and associated academic publications.

LINKS

This deliverable shows the associated online services that give access to CsLoc publication.

Csloc seismic locations are published since October 16th, 2020 on the “[For Seismologist](#)” of the EMSC website under the name CSLC. An example is shown on the Figure 1. Since 2022, July 1st, Csloc solutions are published on the EMSC public web page, as well as on the LastQuake application.

2020-11-18 08:27:46.0	14.88 N	93.32 W	27	M	3.8	M	OFFSHORE CHIAPAS, MEXICO	UNM
2020-11-18 08:26:50.1	20.38 S	68.51 W	125	M	5.0	A	POTOSI, BOLIVIA	SC3
2020-11-18 08:26:48.0	20.31 S	69.14 W	104	ML	4.7	A	TARAPACA, CHILE	CSLC
2020-11-18 08:26:47.0	20.31 S	69.02 W	106	M	4.6	A	TARAPACA, CHILE	GFZ
2020-11-18 08:26:46.6	20.32 S	69.08 W	102	mb	4.8	M	TARAPACA, CHILE	NEIC
2020-11-18 08:26:46.1	20.33 S	68.96 W	108	mb	4.8	M+	TARAPACA, CHILE	INFO
2020-11-18 08:26:27.1	20.46 S	70.00 W	10	mb	4.8	M	TARAPACA, CHILE	RSBR
2020-11-18 08:23:03.0	5.07 N	125.52 E	170	M	3.2	M	MINDANAO, PHILIPPINES	PIVS

Figure 1: CsLoc seismic locations are published on the EMSC website in the For Seismologist section. The full message with the datetime of publication is available inside the CsLoc message.